

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

INVESTIGATION OF THE CuInSe₂-CoSe SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The nature of physicochemical interaction in the CuInSe₂-CoSe system was determined and its phase diagram was constructed using DTA, XRD, MSA, and microhardness measurement methods. The phase diagram of the system is of the eutectic type; the eutectic crystallizes at a temperature of 950°C and a composition of 68 mol% CoSe.

At 810°C, a chalcopyrite \rightleftharpoons sphalerite phase transition occurs in CuInSe₂. High-temperature β -CuInSe₂ forms a eutectic with CoSe. With an increase in the concentration of cobalt selenide, the temperature of the α -CuInSe₂ \rightleftharpoons β -CuInSe₂ polymorphic eutectoid transformation decreases monotonically from 810°C to 660°C.

Solubility based on CuInSe₂ is 10 mol% at room temperature. X-ray diffraction patterns of the studied samples were recorded using the X-ray diffraction method on a Bruker D8 ADVANCE diffractometer.

Microstructure and microhardness analyses were performed on a PMT microscope. It was determined that the sample with a composition of 50 at.% Co + 50 at.% Se is single-phase and has a microhardness of 4850 MPa.

Keywords: eutectic, thermal effect, microhardness, phase diagram, equilibrium.

Introduction

Ternary copper chalcogenides with a chalcopyrite structure are recognized as promising photoelectric materials, and among them, CuInSe₂ occupies a special place. Interest in the chalcopyrite phase of CuInSe₂ is due to the fact that this compound and several phases based on it exhibit photoconductivity with high efficiency [1-3].

The introduction of 3d-transition metals into the structure of CuInSe₂ significantly alters the electro-physical and optical properties of the parent compound; for example, its electrical conductivity can increase by several orders of magnitude [4-14].

The production of homogeneous alloys based on CuInSe₂ with the participation of 3d-transition metals is of great importance. For instance, in [15-17], certain complex phases possessing magnetic ordering at high temperatures were obtained based on the Cu-In-Cr-Se (Te) system.

We have previously studied the CuInSe₂-MeSe systems (where Me = Mn, Fe, Ni). In the present work, the nature of the physicochemical interaction in the CuInSe₂-CoSe system was determined and its phase diagram was constructed using DTA, XRD, MSA, and

microhardness measurement methods. This paper presents a finalized version of the phase diagram for the CuInSe₂-CoSe system, with refined boundaries of solid solutions from the CuInSe₂ side.

Experimental part

Samples of the system were synthesized from high-purity elements (electrolytic copper with an impurity content of less than 0.0001%, In-000 grade indium, OSCh-17-4 selenium, and carbonyl cobalt) in evacuated (~0.1 Pa) quartz ampoules with a gradual increase in temperature up to 1100°C and, in some cases, even higher. The duration of the synthesis was at least 8 hours. To achieve an equilibrium state, the alloys were subjected to homogenizing annealing at 630°C for 100 hours. DTA of the alloys was performed on an N-307/1 two-coordinate potentiometer. A differential-combined version of a chromel-alumel thermocouple was utilized. Calcined Al₂O₃ served as the reference standard. The amount of the alloy sample was generally 1 g. However, in certain cases, to resolve the degeneracy of thermal effects of neighboring phase transitions, the mass of the analyzed samples was reduced to 0.2 g. The results of the DTA and microhardness measurements for the CuInSe₂-CoSe system are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Results of DTA and microhardness measurements of the CuInSe₂-CoSe system

Composition				Thermal effects, °C		H _μ ; MPa	
mol% CoSe	amount of CuInSe ₂ and CoSe in 1 gram,q			Isothermal	Polythermal		
	CuInSe ₂	Co	Se			CuInSe ₂	CoSe
0	1,0000	0	0	810; 986	-	2200	-
5	0,9788	0,0090	0,01210	-	765; 990	2450	-
10	0,9564	0,0186	0,02495	-	775; 970; 985	2580	-
20	0,90702	0,03974	0,05324	-	725; 960; 980	2580	-
30	0,85054	0,06388	0,08558	660	955; 975	2580	-
40	0,78533	0,09175	0,12292	660; 950	975	2575	-
50	0,70920	0,12428	0,16652	660; 950	970	2580	-
60	0,61918	0,16275	0,21807	660; 950	965	2560	-
70	0,51105	0,20896	0,27999	660; 950	970	-	4850
80	0,37877	0,26550	0,35573	660; 950	995	-	4850
90	0,21321	0,33625	0,45054	660	1020	-	4850
100	-	0,42737	0,57263	1055	-	-	4850

Phase diagram of the CuInSe₂-CoSe system, constructed based on the combined data of the above-mentioned physico-chemical analysis methods, is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. a) Phase diagram of the CuInSe₂-CoSe system. b) Dependence of microhardness on composition.

As can be seen, the phase diagram belongs to the eutectic type with limited solubility. It is known that the

sphalerite-chalcopyrite phase transition for the compound CuInSe₂ occurs at 810 °C. The high-temperature modification β-CuInSe₂ forms a eutectic with CoSe.

The eutectic crystallizes at 950 °C and 68 mol.% CoSe. With increasing CoSe concentration, the temperature of the polymorphic eutectoid transformation $\alpha\text{-CuInSe}_2 \rightleftharpoons \beta\text{-CuInSe}_2$ decreases monotonically from 810 to 660 °C.

The solubility based on CuInSe_2 extends up to 22 mol.% at 660 °C and narrows to ~10 mol.% CoSe at room temperature. In the subsolidus region, the alloys consist of a mechanical mixture of α - and γ -phases. Fig.

1b shows the dependence of microhardness on the composition of chalcopyrite phases in the $\text{CuInSe}_2\text{-CoSe}$ system.

It should be noted that the thermal effects at 507 °C and 910 °C reported in [18] for the alloy 50 at.% Co + 50 at.% Se were not observed by us. As noted in [18], the alloy with 50 at.% Se is heterogeneous and consists of a mixture of Co_9Se_8 and the γ -phase.

Table 2 shows the literature and our data on the values of d_α and I_{rel} for the CoSe compound.

Table 2.

Values of d_α and I_{rel} of the CoSe compound.

Our data			Data [18]		Data [21].	
$d_\alpha, \text{Å}^0$	I_{rel}	hkl	$d_\alpha, \text{Å}^0$	I_{OTH}	$d_\alpha, \text{Å}^0$	I_{OTH}
5,08	13		3,62	11	2,05	100
3,00	46		3,10	11	2,40	50
2,68	100		2,65	94	1,71	50
2,38	12		2,30	17	1,07	100
2,02	62		2,10	14	0,96	100
1,84	15		1,98	100	1,08	50
1,80	46		1,78	50	0,99	50
1,74	9		1,50	22		
1,45	22					
1,33	17					

However, the alloy of 1:1 composition synthesized from carbonyl cobalt is homogeneous and consists of a single γ -phase. The thermo gram of this alloy shows one thermal effect at 1052 ± 3 °C. This reversible effect corresponds to the melting temperature of

CoSe [19]. The homogeneity of this alloy is confirmed by XRD, MSA, and microhardness measurements.

The X-ray diffraction patterns of the studied samples were obtained using a Bruker D8 ADVANCE. The diffraction patterns of the initial compounds were compared with literature data [20–22].

Fig. 2. X-ray diffraction patterns of alloys in the system: 1 – CuInSe_2 ; 2 – 5

Fig. 2. Diffraction patterns of alloys of the system: 1-CuInSe₂; 2-5 mol % CoCe; 3-10 mol % CoCe; 4-50 mol % CoCe; 5-CoSe.

The X-ray diffraction pattern of the CuInSe₂ compound corresponds to its chalcopyrite modification [20] with tetragonal lattice parameters $a = 0.578$ nm and $c = 1.1621$ nm. The results of the X-ray phase analysis are presented in Fig. 2. The presence of solubility is confirmed by the shift of diffraction peaks toward higher angles.

Microstructural analysis is used to identify the studied phases and determine their boundaries. This analysis, like other physico-chemical methods, helps to interpret the results of thermal analysis [23–25].

Microstructural analysis is usually carried out at room temperature in reflected light using metallographic microscopes. For this purpose, we used an MIM-7 microscope. Microhardness measurements were performed using a PMT-3 instrument.

First, microsections were prepared. The sample surface was polished by rubbing in one direction with different grades of abrasive paper. Then the surfaces were cleaned of dust and polished to a mirror finish using diamond pastes of various grades and GOI paste. The prepared microsections were first treated with water, then with alcohol or acetone, and dried. In some cases, the phases composing the samples differ only slightly in color and may appear as a single phase under the microscope. In such cases, the presence of a second phase is determined using various etching agents. In our study, a chromium-containing mixture diluted in a ratio of 1:3 (15 ml H₂SO₄ + 0.5 g K₂Cr₂O₇ + 50 ml H₂O) or a mixture of 1N NaOH + 3% H₂O₂ was used.

The choice of etchant and proper indentation are of great importance in microhardness measurement and microstructural analysis. The correct selection of load is essential for accurate determination of microhardness. It has been established that microhardness depends directly on the applied load on the indenter; however, the nature of this dependence has not been fully studied [26,27]. The load is selected according to the individual properties of the initial substances and the new phases formed in each system. The etching time is determined experimentally; in our work, it was approximately 5–15 seconds.

Microstructural analysis is also used to determine the homogeneity limits of solid solutions. It was established that the alloy with a composition of 50 at.% Co + 50 at.% Se is single-phase, and its microhardness is 4850 MPa (load 50 g). In the α -solid solution region, the microhardness varies from 2200 to 2580 MPa. On the CoSe side, the microhardness (4850 MPa) does not change, indicating the absence of CuInSe₂ solubility in CoSe at room temperature.

Thus, the CuInSe₂–CoSe system is quasibinary and of the eutectic type. On the CuInSe₂ side, there is a significant region of solid solutions, where the electrical conductivity of the samples increases sharply with increasing CoSe concentration.

Conclusion

Physicochemical studies have established that the CuInSe₂–CoSe system is quasi-binary and eutectic. On the CuInSe₂ side, there is a significant region of solid

solutions, where the electrical conductivity of the samples increases sharply with increasing CoSe concentration.

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